

Figure 27: The 12 marmans in a 9x9 vāstu. MY 4, as quoted by Trilocana, commenting on SŚ 65a. See MY comm 4, 28v,3.

	marman name	symbol
vaṃśa	—	○
	mahāmarman	⊕
	ambuja	⊛
raju	—	⌢
	a hala is half a samṣṭa	
	svastika	⊕
sirā	—	⊕
	mahāsvastika	⊕
	vajra	✦
	a śūla is half a vajra	
	maṇibandha	◇
	trikaṭa	△
	suviśuddhapada	■

